

Original Research Article

Assessment of the Causes and Effects of Unwanted Teenage Pregnancy in Ifetedo, Ife South Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria*Sesan Emmanuel Busayo¹, Sandra Salomy Phiri², Gloria Oluwaseun Olatunji³¹Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Nigeria²Department of Health and Agriculture, University College Dublin (UCD)³Department of Public Health Science, Kwara State University Malete, Nigeria

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: Teenage is often used interchangeably with adolescence. World Health Organization opined that it is the period between 10 and 19 years when the secondary sex characteristics appear. Turner and Helms (2018) reported that the teen years fall between the ages of 13 and 19 years.

OBJECTIVE: To investigate the causes and effects of unwanted teenage pregnancy in Ifetedo, Ife South Local Government Area, Osun State.

METHODS: A descriptive survey research design was adopted. A sample size of 171 was selected by multistage sampling techniques. Data were collated and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25.

RESULTS: 143 (83.6%) of the respondents agreed that a broken home is a leading cause of teenage pregnancy, and 102 (59.6%) of the respondents agreed that freedom given to a female child can cause pregnancy. 155 (90.6%) of the respondents agreed that lack of parental care is also a factor responsible for teenage pregnancy, and 95 (55.6%) of the respondents agreed that unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to a negative impact on the family, 129 (75.4%) of the respondents agreed that unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to stigmatization. 134 (78.4%) agreed that unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to induced abortion/termination of pregnancy.

CONCLUSION: Teenage pregnancy constitutes a major socio-medical and socio-economic problem and is becoming more prevalent in Nigeria. The emergence of this problem has been attributed to various factors including early exposure to causal sexual activity, peer pressure, lack of sex education, socioeconomic status and family background and others.

Keywords: Causes, Effects, Teenagers, Teenage Pregnancy.

INTRODUCTION

One of the salient responsibilities of women is procreation as ordained by God. However, there are conditions to be met before a woman could start procreating. In African context, the act of procreation is a responsibility of grown up young adults who have been found to be physically, economically, emotionally, spiritually and at large psychologically matured; that is why marriage act is highly contracted and celebrated in our present societies. The observed situation prevalent in both developed and underdeveloped world is such that there are, however, girls as young as ten who are sexually active and occasionally become pregnant and give birth, such that girls of between thirteen and nineteen years are now getting pregnant at an alarming rate (Oguguo, 2015).

Surveys by investigators such as Briggs (2016) and others revealed that teenagers become sexually active at an early age with corresponding high fertility. This condition is widely referred to as teenage pregnancy. Teenage Pregnancy is defined as 'a teenager or under-aged usually within ages of thirteen to nineteen years becoming pregnant'. The term in every day speech usually refers to women who have not reached legal adulthood who become pregnant, (Oguguo, 2015).

Teenage is often used interchangeably with adolescence (Onuzunuke, 2015). World Health Organization {WHO} (2017) opined that, it is the period between 10 and 19 years when the secondary sex characteristics appear. Turner and Helms (2018) reported that the teen years fall between the ages of 13 and 19 years. The issue of pregnancies among teenage girls seems to be one of the social problems facing not only Nigeria, but also several other nations of the world. Teenage sexual activities in Nigeria also tend to be on the increase (Nwosu, 2015).

A major consequence of these increase sexual activities among teenagers is out of wedlock pregnancies that may result in abortion, childbirth or even death. Pregnancy at whatever stage in life can be a life changing experience that cuts across boundaries of race, educational attainment and socio-economic status (Kost, et al., 2019). Motherhood places demands on one's life which were hitherto non-existent prior to the birth of the woman and when a girl that should be in school becomes pregnant, her entire life could be completely altered as her hopes and aspirations could be shattered (Deegan, 2020). Teenage parents according to Kost et al., (2019) are parents between the ages of 13 and 19 years. Kost et al., (2019) believe that teenage pregnancy is a delinquent behavior resulting from stress, dislike, malice, boredom and unhappiness experienced by a teenage girl within her home environment. Other predisposing factors include alcoholism, drug addiction, and sexual promiscuity.

According to Kinby (2016) victims of teenage pregnancy lacked information or probably were not adequately educated on safe-sex either by their parents, schools or development agencies that could have enabled them deal with friends who lure them into sex prematurely. He stressed further that children of single parents are more vulnerable to teenage pregnancy. In the same vein exposure to sexual content on television, sexuality in the media, pornographic and sex chat rooms by teenagers, could most likely tune them to engage in sexual activities (Park, 2018). Acceptance of gift for sex and some adult deliberately taking advantage of poor teenagers, encouraging them into having sex were also noted as factors responsible for teenage pregnancy (United Nation, 2016).

Park (2018) posited that approximately 60% of adolescent mothers live in poverty at the time of the birth of their babies and “approximately 73% go on welfare within 5 years of giving birth”, it's associated motherhood are characterized with shame, disgrace, and school dropout sometimes end up the individual's dreams of achieving higher pursuits. According to United Nation (2016) teenage pregnancy is therefore a major concern to world communities with the United State being at the top with almost 1,000,000 teenage pregnancies each year. Teenage pregnancy has attracted a great deal of concern and attention from religious leaders, the general public, policymakers, and social scientists, particularly in the developed and less developed countries especially in Nigeria. The continuing apprehension about teenage pregnancy is based on the profound impact it can have on the lives of the girls and their children.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted in Ifetedo. Ifetedo is a town in Ife south local government area of osun state with population of about 54,674. Ife South is a Local Government Area in Osun State, Nigeria. Its headquarters are in the town of Ifetedo at 7°11'00"N 4°42'00"E. It has an area of 730 km² and its population was 135,338 at the 2006 census. The postal code of the area is 220. It is made up of many towns and villages. Ife South Local Government Area falls under the Osun-East Senatorial District and it is one of the 30 serving local governments in the area with the head as the Executive Chairman and his subordinates like the Councilors and other Honorable members. Districts Under Ife-South LGA include: Abiri, Aye-Amodo, Ifetedo, Kere, Mefoworade, Oke-Owena, Gbengbeleku, Olode, Osi, Ikija, Ogudu, Ayesan, Aare and Aaye.

Advocacy/Community Entry:

A visit to the head of Ifetedo, Ife South Local Government Area, Osun State was made to discuss the researcher's intentions and seek approval to carry out this study.

Study Population

The study population consist of a target population of 300 pregnant teenage girls.

Study Design

A descriptive survey research design was adopted. This design was chosen because it helped to have an in-depth understanding of the causes and effects of unwanted teenage pregnancy in Ifetedo, Ife South Local Government Area, Osun State. The intended use of this design was consistent with Audu (2017) that pointed out that descriptive research design can be used when collecting information about people's attributes, opinions, habits or any of the variety of education or social issues.

Inclusion criteria

The eligible group that was included in this research were teenage girl children from age 11 years to 19 years.

Exclusion Criteria

Men, teenage boys and mothers were excluded in carrying out this research because they do not fit into the research scale.

Sample size determination

The minimum sample size was used to determine the sample size using the formula for descriptive study. The formula is given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)} \text{ (Yamane Taro, 1967)}$$

Where,

n = desire sample size for the study

N = Population size for the study = 300

e = A value representing how error to allow from estimate in the study.

95% = 0.05, 98% = 0.02, 99% = 0.01 etc.

Therefore, by using this formula, $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$ (N=100, E=0.05)

$$n = \frac{300}{1 + 300(0.05^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{300}{1 + 300 \times 0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{300}{1 + 0.75}$$

$$n = \frac{300}{1.75}$$

$$n = 171.43$$

$$n = 171$$

Sampling techniques

A systematic random sampling technique was adopted to the houses with odd numbers, and every pregnant teenage girl and non-pregnant teenage girls in the house were selected and at the end of the exercise therefore, 70 pregnant teenage girls and 101 teenage girls became participants (respondents).

Research Instrument

The instrument that was used for this study was self-design questionnaire. The questionnaire was titled “causes and effects of teenage pregnancy in Ifetedo, Ife South Local Government Area, Osun State”. It has two sections: A and B. Section A consist biodata of the teenage girls like age, sex, religion and occupation, while section B contained items that were used to answer the research questions relating to the researcher’s topic to get the opinion of the respondents. This was used to collect data from the respondents.

Methods of data collection

The questionnaires were administered on the randomly selected 70 pregnant teen girls and 101 non-pregnant teen girls by the researcher. The copies administered were collected after being answered. Those who could not read had their questions translated and explained to them with their answers written down.

Measurement of variables and data processing

The methods of measurement and analysis was objective based using appropriate statistical tests as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Details of Measurement and Data Analysis

Objectives	Variables	Measurement Scale	Statistical Test Applied
One	Socioeconomic characteristics of teenagers and pregnancy of teens	Interval and Nominal	Descriptive and Chi-Square tests analysis.
Two	Factors responsible for teenage pregnancy	Nominal	Descriptive and Chi-Square tests analysis.
Three	Effects of pregnancy among teens	Nominal	Descriptive and Chi-Square tests analysis.
Four	Effectiveness of extant strategies and teenage pregnancy	Nominal	Descriptive and Chi-Square tests analysis.
Five	Measures to addressing teenage pregnancy	Nominal	Descriptive and Chi-Square tests analysis.

Method of data Analysis

Only completed questionnaires that were correctly filled and returned were treated. In treating these copies, the research questions were analysed using descriptive statistics tool.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical consideration is important in ensuring professional research and are non-intrusive in accomplishing research objectives. For this study, the researchers sought for permission to carry out the study from relevant administrative authorities and confirm that the study is to accomplish academic goals only. The researchers also acknowledged additional sources of information from other scholars. The researchers used a self-developed questionnaire on the respondents to elicit the available data used for this study. The respondent’s consent was sought, and the research procedure was explained and confidentially assured. The questionnaires were collected from the respondents after they were filled.

Validity of the Instrument

A self-structured questionnaire drafted by the researchers was given to four experts in the department of Public Health (Community Health unit) including the researcher’s supervisor. Their suggestions and modifications were effected before the final draft copy of the instrument was produced.

Reliability of the Instrument

A pre-test of the questionnaire was conducted among teenagers in Ifetedo, Ife South Local Government Area, Osun State. The aim of the pre-test exercise was to determine the accuracy, suitability and efficiency of the instrument, and to ascertain any difficulty the researchers may encounter while carrying out the main study. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through split-half method using spearman brown method.

Limitations of the study

The major constraints that were suffered in the course of the study include:

- i. The reluctance of some community members to respond to many of the questions asked; and
- ii. Cultural belief of not saying vulgar (raw) words as regards anything to do with the teenage pregnancy. However, these limitations did not affect the validity and reliability of this study.

Results

Answering of Research Questions

Question 1: What are the socioeconomic characteristics of teenagers in Ifetedo, Ife South Local Government Area, Osun State?

Table 2: Respondents’ socioeconomic Characteristics

Variable	Number	Percentage (%)
Age		
11 -13 years	12	7
14 – 16 years	45	26.3
17-19 years	114	66.7
TOTAL	171	100
Educational Qualification		
Formal education	134	78.3
Non-Formal education	37	21.7
TOTAL	171	100
Marital Status		
Married	39	22.8
Single	123	71.9
Divorced	9	5.2
Widow	–	–
TOTAL	171	100
Religion		

Islam	64	37.4
Christianity	78	45.6
Traditional	29	17.0
TOTAL	171	100

From the table above, more than half 114 (66.7%) of the respondents were aged between 17-19 years, majority 134 (78.3%) of the respondents had formal education, 123 (71.9%) of the respondents were single, 78 (45.6%) of the respondents practice Christianity, 64 (37.4%) practice Islam and 29 (17.0%) were traditionalist.

Question 2: What are the factors responsible for unwanted teenage pregnancy in Ifetedo, Ife South Local Government Area, Osun State?

Table 3: factors responsible for unwanted teenage pregnancy in the study area

Causes of teenage pregnancy	Yes	No	Total
Economic status of the parents is one of the factors responsible for teenage pregnancy	124 (72.5%)	47 (27.5%)	171 (100%)
Economic status of the country is one of the factors responsible for teenage pregnancy	101 (59.1%)	70 (40.9%)	171 (100%)
Broken home is a leading cause of teenage pregnancy	143 (83.6%)	28 (16.4%)	171 (100%)
The freedom given to female child can cause teenage pregnancy	102 (59.6%)	69 (40.4%)	171 (100%)
Lack of parental care is also a factor responsible for teenage pregnancy	155 (90.6%)	16 (9.4%)	171 (100%)
Lack of education is also a factor responsible for teenage pregnancy	158 (92.4%)	13 (7.6%)	171 (100%)
Environmental and societal factor also causes pregnancy	161 (94.2%)	10 (5.8%)	171 (100%)
Termination of studies is one of the causes of teenage pregnancy	136 (79.5%)	35 (20.5%)	171 (100%)

According to table 3, more than half 124 (72.5%) of the respondents agreed that economic status of the parents is one of the factors responsible for teenage pregnancy. 143 (83.6%) of the respondent agreed that broken home is a leading cause of teenage pregnancy, more than half 102 (59.6%) of the respondents agreed that freedom given to female child can cause pregnancy, 155 (90.6%) of the respondents agreed that lack of parental care is also a factor responsible for teenage pregnancy, 158 (92.4%) of the respondents agreed that lack of education is also a factor responsible for teenage pregnancy, 161 (94.2%) of the respondents agreed that environmental and societal factor such as glamorization of pregnancy also cause teenage pregnancy, and 136 (79.5%) of the respondents agreed that termination of studies is one of the causes of teenage pregnancy.

Question 3: What are the effects of unwanted teenage pregnancy in Ifetedo, Ife South Local Government Area, Osun State?

Table 4: effects of unwanted teenage pregnancy in the study area

Effects of unwanted teenage pregnancy	Yes	No	Total
Unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to negative impact on the family	95 (55.6%)	76 (44.4%)	171 (100%)
Unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to negative impact on adolescent's mental health	166 (97.1%)	5 (2.9%)	171 (100%)
Unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to stigmatization	129 (75.4%)	42 (24.6%)	171 (100%)
Unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to induced abortion/termination of pregnancy	134 (78.4%)	37 (21.6%)	171 (100%)
Unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to low birth weight	115 (67.3%)	56 (32.7%)	171 (100%)

From table 4 above, more than half 95 (55.6%) of the respondents agreed that unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to negative impact on family, 166 (97.1%) of the respondents agreed that unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to

negative impact on adolescent's mental health. 129 (75.4%) of the respondents agreed that unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to stigmatization. 134 (78.4%) agreed that unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to induced abortion/termination of pregnancy. And 115 (67.3%) of the respondents agreed that Unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to low birth weight.

DISCUSSION

The analysis revealed that more than half 114 (66.7%) of the respondents were aged between 17-19 years, majority 134 (78.3%) of the respondents had formal education, 123 (71.9%) of the respondents were single, 78 (45.6%) of the respondents practice Christianity, 64 (37.4%) practice Islam and 29 (17.0%) were traditionalist.

Majority 158 (92.4%) of the respondents agreed that lack of education is also a factor responsible for teenage pregnancy. This is a major factor for increasing rate of abortion among teenagers. In compares, this agreed with the findings of Oguguo, (2015) which revealed that lack of sexual education caused teens to get abortions since they realize that they are not ready yet to take responsibility to be a parent at such a young age and they still have many things to chase in life.

Majority 115 (67.3%) of the respondents agreed that Unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to low birth weight, this is in agreement with WHO (1991) which states that complications of pregnancy among teenagers includes first and third trimester's bleeding, severe anaemia, prolonged and obstructed labour, cephalopelvic disproportion, toxaeimias of pregnancy, stillbirth and high prenatal mortality and morbidity. Besides the health consequence of teenage pregnancy, the educational attainment of most, if not all teenage parents are hampered and students who become pregnant rarely go back to school.

Summary

Causes of Teenage Pregnancy

According to table 3, more than half 124 (72.5%) of the respondents agreed that economic status of the parents is one of the factors responsible for teenage pregnancy. 143 (83.6%) of the respondent agreed that broken home is a leading cause of teenage pregnancy, more than half 102 (59.6%) of the respondents agreed that freedom given to female child can cause pregnancy, 155 (90.6%) of the respondents agreed that lack of parental care is also a factor responsible for teenage pregnancy, 158 (92.4%) of the respondents agreed that lack of education is also a factor responsible for teenage pregnancy, 161 (94.2%) of the respondents agreed that environmental and societal factor such as glamorization of pregnancy also cause teenage pregnancy, and 136 (79.5%) of the respondents agreed that termination of studies is one of the causes of teenage pregnancy

Consequences of Teenage Pregnancy

From table 4 above, more than one half 95 (55.6%) of the respondents agreed that unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to negative impact on family, 166 (97.1%) of the respondents agreed that unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to negative impact on adolescent's mental health. 129 (75.4%) of the respondents agreed that unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to stigmatization. 134 (78.4%) agreed that unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to induced abortion/termination of pregnancy. And 115 (67.3%) of the respondents agreed that Unwanted teenage pregnancy can result to low birth weight.

Conclusion

Teenage pregnancy constitutes a major socio-medical and socio-economic problem and is becoming more prevalent in Nigeria. The emergence of this problem has been attributed to various factors including early exposure to causal sexual activity, peer pressure, lack of sex education and others. Socioeconomic status or background is a strong predictor of teenage pregnancy. The rate at which young girls drop out of school these days because they have to focus on caring for their new born is a cause for concern, as they not only end up doing menial jobs to sustain themselves and their offspring, they become an unwelcome burden on their families and the society as a whole. Family relationship is very important in the upbringing of a child. When parents are less concerned about their children, the children tend to misbehave without considering the risks and consequences of such behaviour. The rate of teenage pregnancy can be reduced by offering free and compulsory education to the girl child and educating the populace about the social and medical consequences of teenage pregnancy and the dangers associated with early motherhood. The negative effects of adolescent motherhood on women call for a more rigorous and wholesome sex education (Fadeyi, 2019). According to an NGO, Partnership for advocacy in child and family health (PACFAH), says that increase access to family planning can prevent about 1.6million unintended pregnancies yearly in Nigeria (UN, 2016). The NGO representative said that the (FPL) helped to save the lives of women and children by reducing unplanned pregnancies and promoting health child spacing. Evidence show that the high rate of Maternal and child mortality is largely due to unwanted pregnancies and low use of family planning services.

Recommendations

There is an urgent need to reduce teenage pregnancy among teenage girls in Nigeria. The following are hereby recommended:

- Parent's value, parental regulations and parent-child connectedness (support, closeness, and warmth) can help to lower teenage pregnancy.
- The government should set up counselling centers in all cities and local government headquarters where teenagers can go for counselling on issues bothering them including their sexual life. Majority of the teenagers cannot open up to their parents on issues bothering on their sexual life.
- Teenagers should be taught abstinence and how to defer sexual gratification till after marriage.
- Families should ensure that they develop a close relationship with their children. They should know the friends their children keep and educate them on when to have intimate relationship with opposite sex.
- Keeping adolescent girls in schools, using economic incentives and livelihood programs can help reduce teenage pregnancy
- Socioeconomic status of families should not be an excuse for female children to get pregnant.
- Families should ensure teenage girls are well educated either in the four walls of a classroom or in a vocational training centre.

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